

**PHARMACOGNOSTICAL, PHYSICOCHEMICAL AND HPTLC
EVALUATION OF DEVADARVYADI CHOORNA****Dr. Sreeraj R.*¹, Dr. Nikhil Neelakandhan E. U.², Dr. Madhavi S. Deodas³**

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ABSTRACT

Devadarvyadi Choorna is a classical Ayurvedic polyherbal formulation mentioned in Charaka Samhita Kasa Chikitsa Adhyaya. The formulation contains Devadaru, Abhaya, Mustha, Pippali and Shunthi. The present article compiles pharmacognostical, physicochemical and HPTLC evaluation findings of Devadarvyadi Choorna. Organoleptic evaluation revealed a light brown fine powder with characteristic odour and taste. Powder microscopy demonstrated annular vessels, bordered pitted vessels, fibres, cork cells, calcium oxalate crystals and starch grains. Physicochemical parameters and heavy metal analysis were within acceptable limits. HPTLC fingerprinting demonstrated multiple phytochemical constituents with reproducible chromatographic profiles at 254 nm and 366 nm. The analytical findings support the quality, safety and standardization of the formulation.

KEYWORDS: Devadarvyadi Choorna, HPTLC,

Pharmacognosy, Standardization, Ayurveda.

INTRODUCTION

Devadarvyadi Choorna^[1] is a classical Ayurvedic formulation described in Charaka Samhita

under Kasa Chikitsa Adhyaya. The formulation is traditionally indicated in respiratory disorders^[2] and cough. It contains Devadaru^[3] (*Cedrus deodara*)^[4], Abhaya^[5] (*Terminalia chebula*)^[6], Mustha^[7] (*Cyperus rotundus*)^[8], Pippali^[9] (*Piper longum*)^[10] and Shunthi^[11] (*Zingiber officinale*).^[12] Standardization of herbal formulations is essential to ensure quality, efficacy and safety. The present article consolidates the analytical findings from pharmacognostical, physicochemical and chromatographic evaluation reports.

Ingredients of Devadarvyadi Choorna

SI No	Ingredient	Botanical Name
1	Devadaru	<i>Cedrus deodara</i>
2	Abhaya	<i>Terminalia chebula</i>
3	Mustha	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>
4	Pippali	<i>Piper longum</i>
5	Shunthi	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>

Organoleptic Evaluation

The organoleptic evaluation revealed that Devadarvyadi Choorna is a fine powder with light brown colour, characteristic odour and characteristic taste. Uniform texture and colour indicate proper processing and mixing of ingredients.

Powder Microscopy Analysis

Microscopic evaluation demonstrated important diagnostic characters such as annular vessels, spiral vessels, bordered pitted vessels, fibres, cork cells, medullary rays, sclereids, calcium oxalate crystals, tracheids and starch grains. These findings confirm the botanical authenticity of the formulation.

Figure: Powder microscopy and analytical image of Devadarvyadi Choorna.

winCATS Planar Chromatography Manager

Development - Glass tank

Chamber type	Twin Trough Chamber 20x10cm
Executed by	SARANYA
Comment	Saturday, May 11, 2024 3:54:47 PM
Pre-conditioning	30 MINS
Mobile phase	TOLUENE:CHLOROFORM: METHANOL (8:3:1)
Solvent front position	85.0 mm
Volume	10.0 ml
Drying device	Oven
Temperature	60 °C
Time	5 Minutes
Notes	

Detection - CAMAG TLC Scanner

Information	
Application position	10.0 mm
Solvent front position	85.0 mm
Instrument	CAMAG TLC Scanner "Scanner_171019" S/N 171019 (2.01.02)
Executed by	SARANYA
Number of tracks	3
Position of first track X	12.5 mm
Distance between tracks	12.5 mm
Scan start pos. Y	5.0 mm
Scan end pos. Y	85.0 mm
Slit dimensions	4.00 x 0.30 mm, Micro
Optimize optical system	Light
Scanning speed:	20 mm/s
Data resolution:	100 µm/step

Integration

Properties	
Data filtering	Savitsky-Golay 7
Baseline correction	Lowest Slope
Peak threshold min. slope	5
Peak threshold min. height	10 AU
Peak threshold min. area	50
Peak threshold max. height	990 AU
Track start position	5.0 mm
Track end position	75.0 mm
Display scaling	Automatic

Measurement Table

Wavelength	254
Lamp	D2 & W
Measurement Type	Remission
Measurement Mode	Absorption
Optical filter	Second order
Detector mode	Automatic
PM high voltage	189 V

Detector properties

Y-position for 0 adjust	5.0 mm
Track # for 0 adjust	0
Analog Offset	10%
Sensitivity	Automatic (147)

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Figure: Powder microscopy and analytical image of Devadarvyadi Choorna.

Physicochemical Evaluation

Parameter	Unit	Result	Method
Loss on Drying	% w/w	7.33	API Part I Vol I
Total Ash	% w/w	5.31	IP 2018
Acid Insoluble Ash	% w/w	0.71	IP 2018
pH (10% aqueous solution)	-	4.29	API Part I Vol I
Water Soluble Extract	% w/w	27.61	IP 2018
Alcohol Soluble Extract	% w/w	26	IP 2018

Heavy Metal Analysis

Parameter	Result	Specification	Detection Limit	Method
Arsenic	0.17 ppm	NMT 3.0	0.05	CKL/ANL/AY-008
Lead	0.95 ppm	NMT 10.0	0.05	CKL/ANL/AY-008
Mercury	Not Detected	NMT 1.0	0.05	CKL/ANL/AY-008
Cadmium	0.05 ppm	NMT 0.3	0.05	CKL/ANL/AY-008

HPTLC Analysis

High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography (HPTLC) was performed to evaluate the chromatographic fingerprint profile of Devadarvyadi Choorna. The analysis showed multiple phytochemical peaks indicating the presence of diverse constituents.

HPTLC Methodology

Parameter	Details
Stationary Phase	Silica gel 60 F254
Plate Size	5 x 10 cm
Application Instrument	CAMAG Linomat 5
Mobile Phase	Toluene : Chloroform : Methanol (8:3:1)
Development Chamber	Twin Trough Chamber
Pre-conditioning	30 minutes
Drying Condition	60°C for 5 minutes
Detection Instrument	CAMAG TLC Scanner
Scanning Wavelengths	254 nm and 366 nm

Representative Peak Data

Peak No	Max Rf	Area %	Observation
1	-0.02	15.06	Initial major peak
3	0.08	6.57	Moderate peak
4	0.12	6.20	Distinct peak
9	0.43	52.38	Major dominant peak
11	0.71	2.42	Minor peak

Chromatographic Profiles and Graphs

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Figure: HPTLC chromatographic profile / graph of Devadarvyadi Choorna.

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Peak	Start Rf	Start Height	Max Rf	Max Height	Max %	End Rf	End Height	Area	Area %	Assigned substance
1	-0.06	5.9	-0.02	792.1	20.06	0.02	356.7	27875.5	15.06	unknown *
2	0.03	356.7	0.04	385.0	9.75	0.05	341.3	6925.7	3.74	unknown *
3	0.06	341.5	0.08	439.8	11.14	0.10	376.1	12157.6	6.57	unknown *
4	0.10	377.2	0.12	455.1	11.52	0.13	347.6	11467.3	6.20	unknown *
5	0.13	348.5	0.14	357.8	9.06	0.16	206.8	5893.2	3.18	unknown *
6	0.16	207.2	0.17	231.4	5.86	0.22	136.1	8097.1	4.37	unknown *
7	0.22	136.3	0.23	155.0	3.92	0.25	118.1	3530.8	1.91	unknown *
8	0.25	118.7	0.27	180.5	4.57	0.29	131.2	3769.5	2.04	unknown *
9	0.29	131.3	0.43	743.3	18.82	0.59	60.6	96949.7	52.38	unknown *
10	0.60	60.7	0.62	73.1	1.85	0.66	35.6	2907.3	1.57	unknown *
11	0.67	33.3	0.71	103.1	2.61	0.76	28.4	4482.7	2.42	unknown *
12	0.76	28.6	0.78	33.0	0.84	0.82	2.8	1027.3	0.56	unknown *

Track 2, ID: DEVADARVYADI YOGA CHOORNA

Peak	Start Rf	Start Height	Max Rf	Max Height	Max %	End Rf	End Height	Area	Area %	Assigned substance
1	-0.04	1.6	-0.02	812.1	21.94	0.02	376.7	26930.9	14.30	unknown *
2	0.03	378.4	0.03	398.0	10.75	0.05	352.2	6424.1	3.41	unknown *
3	0.05	353.1	0.08	451.5	12.20	0.09	389.8	12617.3	6.70	unknown *
4	0.09	390.1	0.12	466.9	12.61	0.16	221.2	18407.9	9.77	unknown *
5	0.16	222.8	0.17	246.7	6.67	0.21	152.5	7771.9	4.13	unknown *
6	0.22	152.0	0.23	167.2	4.52	0.25	130.6	3868.7	2.05	unknown *
7	0.25	131.2	0.27	189.2	5.11	0.29	139.1	4330.9	2.30	unknown *
8	0.29	139.8	0.43	751.2	20.30	0.59	65.5	99022.4	52.58	unknown *
9	0.59	65.5	0.62	78.2	2.11	0.67	36.1	3391.5	1.80	unknown *
10	0.67	35.8	0.71	105.1	2.84	0.75	31.2	4608.3	2.45	unknown *
11	0.76	30.0	0.78	35.0	0.95	0.82	2.2	951.8	0.51	unknown *

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Figure: HPTLC chromatographic profile / graph of Devadarvyadi Choorana.

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Track 3, ID: DEVADARVYADI YOGA CHOORNA

Peak	Start Rf	Start Height	Max Rf	Max Height	Max %	End Rf	End Height	Area	Area %	Assigned substance
1	-0.06	7.0	-0.02	781.8	20.16	0.02	365.1	31117.7	16.72	unknown *
2	0.02	366.8	0.03	384.5	9.91	0.04	334.5	5828.4	3.13	unknown *
3	0.05	335.1	0.08	426.3	10.99	0.09	375.0	13823.9	7.43	unknown *
4	0.09	376.2	0.11	444.3	11.46	0.13	344.4	11272.5	6.06	unknown *
5	0.13	346.9	0.13	354.6	9.14	0.15	204.2	5546.3	2.98	unknown *
6	0.16	205.0	0.17	227.6	5.87	0.21	136.4	7606.6	4.09	unknown *
7	0.22	136.8	0.23	155.3	4.00	0.25	117.6	3390.9	1.82	unknown *
8	0.25	117.8	0.26	171.0	4.41	0.28	124.0	4032.7	2.17	unknown *
9	0.29	124.7	0.43	734.1	18.93	0.59	58.3	95772.9	51.47	unknown *
10	0.60	59.3	0.62	70.0	1.81	0.65	38.6	2486.3	1.34	unknown *
11	0.66	30.8	0.71	98.0	2.53	0.76	25.6	4370.9	2.35	unknown *
12	0.76	25.9	0.77	30.8	0.79	0.81	5.0	825.9	0.44	unknown *

Measurement Table

Wavelength	366
Lamp	Hg
Measurement Type	Remission
Measurement Mode	Fluorescence
Optical filter	K400
Detector mode	Automatic
PM high voltage	189 V

Detector properties

Y-position for 0 adjust	5.0 mm
Track # for 0 adjust	0
Analog Offset	10%
Sensitivity	Automatic (147)

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Figure: HPTLC chromatographic profile / graph of Devadarvyadi Choorna.

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All tracks at WavelengthSc4

Track 1, ID: DEVADARVYADI YOGA CHOORNA

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Page 6 of 12**Figure: HPTLC chromatographic profile / graph of Devadarvyadi Choorna.**

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Peak	Start Rf	Start Height	Max Rf	Max Height	Max %	End Rf	End Height	Area	Area %	Assigned substance
1	-0.06	25.9	-0.06	26.7	0.83	-0.05	0.7	167.2	0.17	unknown *
2	-0.04	0.0	-0.01	227.7	7.07	0.01	169.6	4128.1	4.25	unknown *
3	0.01	171.2	0.03	347.2	10.78	0.03	238.9	4869.3	5.01	unknown *
4	0.03	241.6	0.04	282.5	8.77	0.05	217.9	3520.4	3.62	unknown *
5	0.05	220.6	0.07	786.9	24.44	0.11	141.6	19957.5	20.54	unknown *
6	0.11	142.5	0.12	159.6	4.96	0.17	57.1	5882.2	6.05	unknown *
7	0.18	57.9	0.22	132.1	4.10	0.25	78.9	5532.0	5.69	unknown *
8	0.27	75.7	0.28	83.1	2.58	0.32	43.5	2457.8	2.53	unknown *
9	0.32	43.6	0.35	62.4	1.94	0.37	52.5	2269.9	2.34	unknown *
10	0.37	52.6	0.41	77.0	2.39	0.42	72.9	2614.7	2.69	unknown *
11	0.43	73.0	0.45	112.9	3.50	0.48	99.3	3938.0	4.05	unknown *
12	0.48	99.5	0.55	328.8	10.21	0.59	218.6	18441.6	18.98	unknown *
13	0.59	218.8	0.60	219.7	6.82	0.67	20.2	6956.4	7.16	unknown *
14	0.70	21.5	0.77	373.7	11.60	0.87	0.0	16425.3	16.91	unknown *

Track 2, ID: DEVADARVYADI YOGA CHOORNA

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Figure: HPTLC chromatographic profile / graph of Devadarvyadi Choorna.

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Peak	Start Rf	Start Height	Max Rf	Max Height	Max %	End Rf	End Height	Area	Area %	Assigned substance
1	-0.05	0.0	-0.03	50.1	1.54	-0.02	43.6	596.3	0.61	unknown *
2	-0.02	45.5	-0.01	227.5	7.00	0.01	174.7	3305.6	3.37	unknown *
3	0.01	175.9	0.02	337.0	10.37	0.03	237.1	4627.2	4.72	unknown *
4	0.03	241.1	0.04	271.8	8.36	0.05	208.5	3401.5	3.47	unknown *
5	0.05	210.4	0.07	806.7	24.82	0.11	137.2	20517.3	20.92	unknown *
6	0.11	138.5	0.12	157.1	4.83	0.17	56.8	5743.9	5.86	unknown *
7	0.17	57.3	0.22	131.2	4.04	0.27	76.5	6368.2	6.49	unknown *
8	0.27	76.8	0.28	84.9	2.61	0.32	42.4	2456.7	2.50	unknown *
9	0.32	42.5	0.35	63.4	1.95	0.37	53.0	2261.5	2.31	unknown *
10	0.37	53.0	0.41	77.3	2.38	0.42	72.3	2626.9	2.68	unknown *
11	0.42	72.4	0.45	111.5	3.43	0.48	99.1	3973.3	4.05	unknown *
12	0.48	99.3	0.55	329.8	10.15	0.59	220.5	17799.4	18.14	unknown *
13	0.59	220.6	0.60	222.2	6.84	0.67	20.7	7839.2	7.99	unknown *
14	0.70	22.1	0.78	379.3	11.67	0.87	0.1	16579.4	16.90	unknown *

Track 3, ID: DEVADARVYADI YOGA CHOORNA

Peak	Start Rf	Start Height	Max Rf	Max Height	Max %	End Rf	End Height	Area	Area %	Assigned substance
1	-0.03	44.1	-0.01	221.2	7.49	0.01	175.0	3501.1	3.65	unknown *
2	0.01	176.2	0.02	347.6	11.78	0.03	233.6	4413.2	4.60	unknown *
3	0.03	235.6	0.03	272.8	9.24	0.05	212.6	3418.0	3.57	unknown *
4	0.05	215.6	0.07	804.2	27.25	0.10	138.3	20605.3	21.50	unknown *
5	0.10	138.5	0.11	156.5	5.30	0.17	57.5	5815.6	6.07	unknown *
6	0.17	58.3	0.21	130.7	4.43	0.26	73.6	6305.9	6.58	unknown *
7	0.26	73.7	0.27	81.4	2.76	0.31	42.2	2348.2	2.45	unknown *
8	0.31	42.4	0.34	65.5	2.22	0.37	53.9	2340.2	2.44	unknown *
9	0.37	54.0	0.40	77.1	2.61	0.42	73.4	2666.2	2.78	unknown *
10	0.42	73.4	0.45	109.9	3.72	0.47	93.8	3334.6	3.48	unknown *
11	0.47	94.0	0.55	323.7	10.97	0.67	19.9	25559.4	26.67	unknown *
12	0.70	22.1	0.77	360.7	12.22	0.84	8.1	15541.6	16.21	unknown *

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Figure: HPTLC chromatographic profile / graph of Devadarvyadi Choorana.

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Image information - 366 nm - Image1

Illumination instrument	CAMAG Visualizer : 171217 (Visualizer_171217)
Digital camera type : snr & Lens	DXA252 : 490823510, Computar, 12 mm, f4.0
Created by : on	SARANYA : Saturday, May 11, 2024 3:55:12 PM
Resolution	Full
Plate border size	-2 mm
Automatic capture	Off
Save mode	Lossy (JPG)
Exposure mode	Automatic, digital level: 85 %, Band

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Figure: HPTLC chromatographic profile / graph of Devadarvyadi Choorna.

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Capture settings:

Image size: 343 Pxl x 715 Pxl (0.13 mm/Pxl)
Exposure : 965.77 ms gain: 1.00
White balance R: 1.40, G: 1.00, B: 1.20
Illumination type / correction type : 366 nm remission : Default correction

Display settings:

White balance: R: 1.00 G: 1.00 B: 1.00
Contrast enhancement: 1.41 (modified)
Brightness: 0.00
Accentuation: 0.80
Color saturation: 1.30 *
Blank plate compensation : N/A

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Figure: HPTLC chromatographic profile / graph of Devadarvyadi Choorna.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The chromatographic fingerprint profile showed multiple peaks representing different phytochemical constituents present in Devadarvyadi Choorna. Major peaks near Rf 0.43 indicated dominant phytoconstituents. The UV visualized plate images at 254 nm and 366 nm

demonstrated reproducible fluorescent and absorbance bands. Physicochemical parameters such as ash values, extractive values and pH were within acceptable limits. Heavy metal analysis showed that arsenic, lead, mercury and cadmium levels were within permissible limits, indicating safety of the formulation.

CONCLUSION

The present study confirms the pharmacognostical authenticity, physicochemical quality and chromatographic consistency of Devadarvyadi Choorna. HPTLC fingerprinting provides a reliable method for standardization and quality control of the formulation. The findings support the use of modern analytical methods for evaluation of classical Ayurvedic formulations.

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